

DISAGGREGATED EFFECTS OF GENDER INEQUALITY IN EDUCATION ON OUTPUT GROWTH IN NIGERIA

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ABSTRACT

This study analyzed how different dimensions of gender inequality in education influence output growth in Nigeria. It utilized time-series data from 1990 to 2023 obtained from the World Bank (2024). The Autoregressive Distributed Lag (ARDL) approach was applied to estimate the model. The results indicate that achieving gender parity in primary school enrollment significantly enhances output growth in both the short and long run. The study also found that gender parity in tertiary education promotes growth in the short run, although its effect becomes insignificant over the long run. Additionally, parity in secondary school enrollment exerts a significant long-run positive effect on growth but shows no significant impact in the short run. Based on these outcomes, the study recommends that the government strengthen efforts to achieve gender parity across all educational levels by addressing barriers faced by girls, including through interventions such as scholarships and conditional cash transfer programs.

Keywords: School Enrollments, Literacy Rates, Gender Parity Index, Output Growth, Autoregressive Distributed Lag Model.

JEL Code: I25, J16, O40, O47

1. INTRODUCTION

Gender inequality remains a barrier to the growth and development of any nation. It is so imperative that the United Nation's Sustainable Development Goals (SDG) 5 aims to achieve gender equality for all segment of society by empowering women and girls (United Nations, 2023). A country experiences faster growth when both men and women contribute optimally to production (Lucas, 1988; Romer, 1990). Following the endogenous growth theory, (Mbatha, 2024) stated that unequal access to education hinders innovation, slows down skill acquisition, and ultimately decreases human capital growth and productivity.

Globally, The United Nations Educational Scientific and Cultural Organization (UNESCO) (2024) reported that 118.5 million girls of primary and secondary school age remain out of school, many concentrated in fragile and low-income economies. In Africa, gender inequality manifests in interconnected social, economic, and cultural forms. Women in Sub-Saharan Africa spend nearly three times more hours on unpaid care work than men, limiting time for

schooling, skills training, and formal employment (African Development Bank, 2023). UNESCO (2024) estimated that 28 million school-aged girls are out of school in the region, disproportionately in rural and conflict-affected areas.

In Nigeria, despite the significance of gender equality for national growth and development, a considerable gender gap still exists in the education sector. In 2024, Nigeria ranked 124th out of 148 countries, with a gender gap score of 0.84, just eight ranks above the lowest performer. Examining school enrollments at every level reveal that the gender parity index for primary school enrollment was 0.98 in 2024, indicating a slight disadvantage for girls (for every 100 male pupils, there were 98 female pupils). However, the parity for secondary and tertiary education was much lower, with indexes of 0.93 and 0.86, respectively. This means, for every 100 male students in secondary school, there were 93 female students, and for every 100 male students in tertiary education, there were 86 female students (World Bank, 2024). Literacy gaps are also significant; with female literacy rates about 12 percentage points lower than those of males (GP1 of 0.88 for youth aged 15-24). These disparities are even more pronounced in rural and northern regions, driven by cultural norms, insecurity, and early marriage (World Bank, 2024).

Gender inequality can hinder output growth. Between 2015 and 2023, when gender inequality was high across all education levels, GDP per capita growth fell below 2%, and was negative in some years (World Bank, 2024). The link between gender inequality in education and output growth is not well defined in existing literature. Ogunjobi et al. (2024) and Adeleke et al. (2024) found that equal participation of men and women in education raises income and productivity. Conversely, Egbulonu and Eleonu (2018) argued that gender disparity alone does not ensure increased productivity if the rise in enrollment does not lead to meaningful economic participation.

Given the uncertainties and the lack of empirical studies in this field within Nigeria, this research seeks to further explore the connection between gender inequality in education and output growth in the country. Additionally, the existing studies have not differentiated the disparities in school enrollments - primary, secondary, and tertiary. Therefore, this paper's key contribution is its examination of the disaggregated effects of gender inequality in education on output growth in Nigeria. It assesses inequality in school enrollments across all levels while also capturing the inequality in literacy rate. Investigating this relationship will yield valuable insights for policymakers, which are crucial for achieving both the SDG targets and Nigeria's long-term development goals.

The remainder of this study is organized as follows: section two reviews the empirical literature, while section three outlines the theoretical framework and methodology. Section four analyzes the results along with their policy implications, and the final section offers appropriate conclusions and policy recommendations.

2. LITERATURE REVIEW

2.1 Theoretical Review

The relationship between gender inequality and output growth can be examined through several theoretical perspectives. One prominent theory is human capital theory, introduced by Becker (1964). He argued that economic growth and development depend on human capital, which includes skills, health, and knowledge. Therefore, unequal access to these resources directly affects productivity and has long-term effects. Gender inequality hinders the complete development and use of human capital, especially in countries like Nigeria, where women and girls face significant educational and health challenges (Ibrahim, 2025).

From the viewpoint of Endogenous Growth Theory, developed by Romer (1990) and Lucas (1988), knowledge creation, innovation, and human capital are key drivers of productivity. Unlike the Solow model, which views technological progress as external, endogenous growth theory claims that policies, education systems, institutional structures, and inclusivity in innovation shape economic paths. The theory suggests that keeping women out of educational, scientific, and innovative fields limits the economy's capacity to innovate and grow from within.

Another framework is the Capability Approach proposed by Sen (1999). Amartya Sen redefines development as expanding individuals' freedoms - their ability to lead valuable lives. This approach shifts the focus from measuring wealth and economic output to improving human well-being and agency. Gender inequality reflects a denial of women's abilities, which restricts not only their personal growth but also society's overall development. Sen (1999) contended that poverty should be viewed as a lack of capabilities, not just low income. In Nigeria, many women experience various forms of deprivation, including inadequate access to quality education, healthcare, financial services, legal rights, and political representation, which collectively limit their freedom to engage fully in economic and social life.

Lastly, Gender-aware Macroeconomics is another perspective linked to scholars like Elson (1995) and Seguino (2000). They criticized traditional macroeconomic models for ignoring gender dynamics in fiscal, monetary, and trade policies. This theory argues that macroeconomic policy is not neutral concerning gender, as it influences men and women differently based on their roles in both paid and unpaid work. A key point of Gender-Aware Macroeconomics is that women suffer more from cuts in public spending, especially in health, education, and social services, where they are both significant employees and beneficiaries. In Nigeria, austerity measures enacted during fiscal crises have led to reduced public sector jobs, which particularly affect women in teaching, nursing, and administrative positions.

2.2 Empirical Review

The impact of gender inequality in education on economic growth is becoming a pressing issue in development economics, particularly for countries like Nigeria that face significant structural challenges. There has been limited research on the link between gender inequality in education and economic growth. However, the available studies have shown that gender inequality in education harms income and output growth. A panel study by Altuzarra et al. (2021) in developing countries found that gender equality in education greatly improves economic growth, especially in sub-Saharan Africa. Their findings stress that educational investments should not only increase access but also be inclusive across genders and continue beyond primary education. Mbatha (2024) supported this view by arguing that unequal access to education limits innovation, slows down skill acquisition, and ultimately reduces human capital, clearly linking gender inequality to stagnant productivity.

Wang et al. (2023) using the generalized method of moment method on panel data of 17 SSA countries from 2005 to 2020 found the impact of gender parity in education and primary school enrollment to be positive and significant on economic growth and concluded that a focused policy in the area of improving the parity in education will enhance productivity and economic growth among the selected SSA countries.

To explore the connection between gender inequality and economic growth in Nigeria, Ogunjobi et al. (2024) applied the ARDL technique from 1981 to 2018. They discovered that increased government spending on education positively affects per capita income, particularly when considering both male and female labor participation. Their study highlighted the multiplier effect of educational investments when access is equal for both genders. Adeleke et

al. (2024) strengthened this connection by analyzing data from 1991 to 2022. They found that educational gender inequality negatively impacts long-term growth, even though short-term gains arise from small increases in enrollment. They argue that long-term growth relies more on sustained female progress in secondary and tertiary education, which leads to higher productivity. Okechukwu et al. (2023) found historical legacies and cultural norms as a contributing factor to gender inequality often limiting women from access to education and hence impacting negatively on their productivity. Obiageli et al. (2022) used the ARDL technique to examine the relationship between education for women and national development in Nigeria and found that when more women are given secondary and tertiary education, there is a significant boost in productivity and child welfare emphasizing on the need to improve education at all levels.

However, education alone does not ensure economic inclusion. Labor market disparities remain persistent and structural. Egbulonu and Eleonu (2018) found that while male school enrollment positively correlates with growth, it is female employment that has a stronger and statistically significant effect on GDP. This indicates that educational attainment is not enough unless it leads to meaningful economic participation.

Clearly, there is limited research on gender inequality in the education sector within the Nigerian context. Among the studies that have examined the relationship between gender inequality and economic growth, none have disaggregated the disparities in school enrollment across all levels, including primary, secondary, and tertiary education. The closest study to this was Wang et al. (2023), however the study only focused on enrollment at the primary level and failed to capture inequality in secondary and tertiary enrollment. Moreover, the study was done in SSA where Nigeria was given little attention. This study aims to address that gap. Although Obiageli et al. (2022) is a related study for the fact that they examine the role of female enrollments at all levels of education on economic growth. They however, failed to address the disparities in enrollments at all levels. This study will fill this gap by examining the impact of gender gap in school enrollments at all levels of education on output growth in Nigeria. It will also examine the impact of gender gap in literacy rate on output growth in Nigeria.

3. METHODOLOGY

3.1 Theoretical Framework

This study is anchored on the Endogenous Growth Theory (EGT) by Romer (1990) and Lucas (1988). The EGT argues that education enhances the productivity of labour by increasing skills, knowledge, and innovation capacity. Human capital accumulation is not subject to diminishing returns in the same way as physical capital; rather, it generates positive externalities that can sustain growth indefinitely. The general functional form of the production process in EGT can be expressed as:

$$Y_t = A(H_t, K_t) \cdot f(K_t, L_t) \text{ ----- [1]}$$

Where: Y_t is total output, K_t is physical capital, L_t is labor, and H_t represents the average human capital stock in the economy, influenced directly by education and learning. The term $A(H_t, K_t)$ captures technology and productivity, both of which are enhanced by a better-educated workforce. Gender inequality in education reduces H_t because a significant proportion of the population women is prevented from fully contributing to the national stock of human capital. This lower human capital stock diminishes innovation potential, slows knowledge diffusion, and reduces the marginal productivity of other inputs such as physical capital. The implication is that even if physical investment levels remain constant, output growth will lag due to the lower quality and inclusiveness of human capital. EGT model predicts that these disparities directly depress long-term output growth. The positive feedback loop whereby higher

education levels drive innovation, which in turn fuels further growth, is weakened when half the population cannot fully access quality education.

3.2 Model Specification

Anchored on the Endogenous growth theory, the model for this study was adapted from the work of Obiageli et al. (2022) where the impact of female enrollment at all levels were examined on economic growth in Nigeria. This study made modifications to their model by using Gender parity in enrollment rather than the absolute enrollment of females as shown in equation 2:

$$GDPPCGR = f (GPILR, GPISEP, GPISES, GPISET, GEX) \text{ ----- [2]}$$

The econometric form of the model is stated in Equation 3

$$GDPPCGR_t = \beta_0 + \beta_1 GPILR_t + \beta_2 GPISEP_t + \beta_3 GPISES_t + \beta_4 GPISET_t + \beta_5 GEX_t + \epsilon_t \quad [3]$$

Where:

GDPPCGR = Gross Domestic Product Per Capita growth rate (Proxy for output growth)

GPILR = Gender Parity Index in Literacy Rate

GPISEP = Gender Parity Index in Primary School Enrollment

GPISES = Gender Parity Index in Secondary School Enrollment

GPISET = Gender Parity Index in Tertiary School Enrollment

GEX = Government Education Expenditure

$\beta_1 - \beta_5 > 0$ (Gender Parity in School Enrollment and literacy is expected to bring about increase in economic growth. Similarly, increase in government education expenditure will boost productivity).

Table 1: Variables Description and Units of Measurement

Variables	Measurement	Source
Gross Domestic Product Per Capital Growth Rate (GDPPCGR)	Annual percentage growth rate of GDP per capita based on constant local currency. It was used as proxy for output growth.	World Bank
Gender Parity Index in Literacy Rate (GPILR)	Gender parity index for youth literacy rate is the ratio of females to males ages 15-24 who can both read and write with understanding a short simple statement about their everyday life.	World Bank
Gender Parity Index in Primary School Enrollment (GPISEP)	Gender parity index for gross enrollment ratio in primary education is the ratio of girls to boys enrolled at primary level in public and private schools.	World Bank
Gender Parity Index in Secondary School Enrollment (GPISES)	Gender parity index for gross enrollment ratio in secondary education is the ratio of girls to boys enrolled at primary level in public and private schools.	World Bank

Gender Parity Index in Tertiary School Enrollment (GPISSET)	Gender parity index for gross enrollment ratio in tertiary education is the ratio of girls to boys enrolled at Tertiary level in public and private schools.	World Bank
Government Education Expenditure (GEX)	This is the total amount of money spent by the government on education measured as a percentage of total government expenditure	World Bank

Source: Author’s Compilation, 2025

3.3 Nature and Sources of Data

This study used time series secondary data from 1990 to 2023. The dataset includes the Gross Domestic Product Per Capita Growth Rate (GDPPCGR), Government Education Expenditure (GEX), and Gender Parity Index in Education at the primary, secondary, and tertiary levels (GPISSEP, GPISSES, and GPISSET), along with Gender Parity Index in Literacy Rates (GPILR). All these variables were collected from the World Bank (2024). GDPPCGR is the annual percentage growth rate of GDP per capita. GPILR measures the ratio of females to males ages 15-24 who can read and write with understanding a simple statement about their everyday life. The Gender Parity Index for each level of school enrollment (GPISSEP, GPISSES, and GPISSET) shows the ratio of girls to boys enrolled in public and private schools at either the primary, secondary, or tertiary level. A ratio closer to one indicates lower inequality, while a ratio farther from one indicates higher inequality.

3.4 Estimation Technique

The Autoregressive Distributed Lag (ARDL) model, developed by Pesaran, Shin, and Smith (2001), is a popular econometric method for estimating long-run relationships in time series data. This study employed the ARDL technique because the variables were integrated at different orders, such as a mix of I (0) and I(1). The ARDL framework is best suitable to estimate both the short run and long run relationship between the dependent and explanatory variables when all the variables are stationary at most first difference (Pesaran et al., 2001).

To examine the short run and the long run relationship between gender inequality in education and output growth in Nigeria, the ARDL model in Equation 4 was estimated:

$$\begin{aligned}
 \Delta GDPPCGR_t = & \alpha_0 + \sum_{i=1}^p \delta_1 \Delta GDPPCGR_{t-1} + \sum_{i=0}^p \delta_2 \Delta GPILR_{t-1} + \sum_{i=0}^p \delta_3 \Delta GPISSEP_{t-1} \\
 & + \sum_{i=0}^p \delta_4 \Delta GPISSES_{t-1} + \sum_{i=0}^p \delta_5 \Delta GPISSET_{t-1} + \sum_{i=0}^p \delta_6 \Delta GEX_{t-1} \\
 & + \lambda_1 GDPPCGR_{t-1} + \lambda_2 GPILR_{t-1} + \lambda_3 GPISSEP_{t-1} + \lambda_4 GPISSES_{t-1} \\
 & + \lambda_5 GPISSET_{t-1} + \lambda_6 GEX_{t-1} + \phi ECT_{t-1} + u_t \text{ -----} \\
 & \text{----- [4]}
 \end{aligned}$$

All variables are as previously defined. δ_1 to δ_6 are short run coefficients while λ_1 to λ_6 are long run coefficients while the ϕ is the coefficient of the error correction term showing the speed of adjustment from short run disequilibrium to long run equilibrium.

4. RESULT AND DISCUSSIONS OF FINDINGS

4.1 Preliminary Analysis

Table 2: Summary of Descriptive Statistics Result

	<i>RGDPPCGR</i>	<i>GPILR</i>	<i>GPISEP</i>	<i>GPISES</i>	<i>GPISET</i>	<i>GEX</i>
Mean	1.597	0.807	0.899	0.919	0.811	7.757
Median	1.500	0.794	0.873	0.906	0.741	8.030
Maximum	12.276	0.896	1.099	1.256	1.261	12.560
Minimum	4.507	0.767	0.786	0.762	0.653	0.550
Std. Dev.	3.733	0.040	0.087	0.123	0.163	2.396

Source: Author's Compilation, 2025

The average growth rate of real GDP per capita (RGDPPCGR) during the reviewed period is about 1.60 percent, with a highest value of 12.28 percent and a lowest value of -4.51 percent. The Gender Parity Index in Literacy Rate (GPILR) has a mean value of 0.81. This means female literacy levels were, on average, about 81 percent of male literacy levels. The Gender Parity Index in Primary School Enrolment (GPISEP) averages 0.90, indicating that female enrolment in primary schools was usually 90 percent of male enrolment. The Gender Parity Index in Secondary School Enrolment (GPISES) has a mean value of 0.92. This shows that female enrolment at this level averaged 92 percent of male enrolment. The Gender Parity Index in Tertiary School Enrolment (GPISET) has an average of 0.81; this means that female enrolment at this level was, on average, 81 percent of male enrolment. Lastly, Government Education Expenditure (GEX) averages 7.76 percent of total government spending, indicating a moderate commitment to the education sector.

4.2 Pre- Estimation Tests

4.2.1 Unit Root Test

In order to avoid a spurious result, the unit root was tested to determine the stationarity property of the variables used for the analysis. The Augmented Dickey Fuller was employed as seen in

Table 3. Summary of Augmented Dickey Fuller Unit Root Test

Variables	T-Statistics (P-Values)	Critical Values @ 5%	Decision	T-statistics (P-Values)	Critical Values @ 5%	Decision	Order of Integration
<i>RGDP PCGR</i>	-3.742** (0.0333)	-3.553	S	-	-	-	I (0)
<i>GPIL R</i>	-4.565*** (0.0049)	-3.553	S	-	-	-	I (0)
<i>GPISE P</i>	-1.076 (0.9180)	-3.553	NS	-5.026*** (0.002)	-3.558	S	I (1)
<i>GPISE S</i>	-3.089 (0.126)	-3.553	NS	-17.70*** (0.0000)	-3.558	S	I (1)
<i>GPISE T</i>	-1.762 (0.7000)	-3.553	NS	-6.655*** (0.000)	-3.558	S	I (1)
<i>GEX</i>	-3.118 (0.119)	-3.553	NS	-7.898*** (0.000)	-3.558	S	I (1)

*** & ** indicate stationarity at 1% & 5% respectively

S – Stationary, NS- Non-Stationary

Author's Compilation, 2025

The ADF test results showed that RGDPPCGR and GPILR are stationary at level, meaning they are integrated of order zero, I(0). In contrast, GPISEP, GPISES, GPISET, and GEX are non-stationary at level but are stationary at first difference, making them integrated of order one, I(1). This mix of I (0) and I (1) variables supports the use of the ARDL modelling approach.

4.3 Model Estimation

This section presents the summary of the models. It includes the ARDL bound tests, short run, long-run and error correction estimates.

Table 4. Summary of ARDL Bound Test

F-Bounds Test		Null Hypothesis: No levels relationship		
Test Statistic	Value	Signif.	I (0)	I (1)
Asymptotic: n=1000				
F-statistic	6.7151	10%	2.49	3.38
K	5	5%	2.81	3.76
		2.50%	3.11	4.13
		1%	3.5	4.63

Source: Author’s Compilation, 2025

At the 5% significance level, the lower bound critical value, I(0) is 2.81 and the upper bound critical value, I(1) is 3.76. The computed F statistic is 6.7151, which is higher than the upper bound value of 3.76. This means the null hypothesis of no long run relationship is rejected, indicating that there is a statistically significant long run relationship among the variables in the model.

Table 5: Presentation of ARDL Short Run, Long Run and Error Correction Result

Variables	Coefficients	Standard Error	T-statistics	P-value
Short Run				
<i>D(GPILR)</i>	-1.379	2.738	-0.504	0.572
<i>D(GPISEP)</i>	7.516	2.527	2.974	0.025
<i>D(GPISES)</i>	-0.347	2.737	-0.127	0.903
<i>D(GPISET)</i>	6.837	2.175	3.143	0.010
<i>D(GEX)</i>	0.440	0.378	1.164	0.289
<i>ECT</i>	-0.537	0.117	-4.590	0.001
Long Run				
<i>GPILR</i>	-0.301	2.016	-0.150	0.151
<i>GPISEP</i>	4.324	2.060	2.099	0.043
<i>GPISES</i>	5.646	1.480	3.815	0.001
<i>GPISET</i>	0.420	1.387	0.303	0.317
<i>GEX</i>	0.302	0.377	0.801	0.432

Source: Author’s Compilation, 2025

Table 6: Summary of Diagnostic Tests

	Statistic	
Coefficient of Determination	R^2	0.85
Autocorrelation	D.W	1.98
Heteroscedasticity	Breusch-Pagan Godfrey	0.2903
Serial Correlation	Breusch Godfrey	0.5165
Linearity Test	Ramsey	0.336
Normality	Jarque Berra	0.7268

Source: Author’s Compilation, 2025

Cusum and Cusum of Squares Test

Figure 1: Cusum and Cusum of Squares Tests

Source: EViews 13

4.4 Discussion of Results and Policy Implications

From Table 5, the gender parity index in literacy rate (GPILR) shows a negative coefficient in both the short run and the long run. Specifically, a one-unit increase in GPILR is associated with a decrease of 1.379 units in RGDP growth rate in the short run and 0.301 units in the long run. However, these estimates are statistically insignificant at the 5% level, meaning that the negative effect has no meaningful explanatory power within the model. In practical terms, this insignificance suggests that variations in literacy parity between males and females have little measurable effect on economic growth during the study period. This is consistent with Egbulonu and Eleonu (2018), who argue that literacy alone, without complementary technical or higher-level skills, has limited impact on growth. Complementing literacy efforts with skill

acquisition and vocational programs for women and girls may provide more substantial productivity benefits.

Examining school enrollment, parity in primary enrollment has a strong positive effect on output growth in both the short run and the long run. An increase of one unit in GPISEP leads to an increase in output growth by 7.516 units in the short run and 4.324 units in the long run. This underscores the importance of early interventions to eliminate barriers to female enrollment, especially in rural and underserved areas where socio-cultural norms, child labor, and early marriage limit access. Altuzarra et al. (2021) argued that equal access to basic education lays the groundwork for inclusive economic growth by allowing broader participation in productive activities. Therefore, policies like conditional cash transfers, school feeding programs, and community awareness initiatives should be scaled up to ensure that girls are enrolled and retained in school from the start.

Parity in secondary school enrollment shows a negative and insignificant impact on output growth in the short run. An increase of one unit in GPISES results in a 0.347 unit decrease in output growth. This contradicts findings from Adeleke et al. (2024), who reported immediate benefits from gender equality at this education level. This discrepancy may arise from structural barriers in Nigeria, where secondary education often does not lead directly to entry into the labor market due to skills mismatches or limited job opportunities. Therefore, policy makers should integrate skill acquisition programs into secondary schools, particularly for girls, enabling them to make meaningful contributions to productivity and growth. More job opportunities should also be created for female secondary school graduates.

In the long run, however, parity in secondary enrollment has a positive and significant effect on output growth. A one unit increase in GPISES leads to an increase of 5.646 units in output growth. This indicates that over time, achieving gender parity in secondary education is crucial for maintaining productivity growth, likely because it helps create a more balanced and versatile workforce. These findings align with the work of Adeleke et al. (2024), who stressed the lasting importance of gender equality at the secondary level for workforce development. Therefore, the government should promote policies that support girls' transition from primary to secondary school and ensure they complete their education. Investing in safe school infrastructure, offering scholarships aimed at girls, especially in STEM fields, and providing mentorship programs can help achieve this goal, particularly in areas affected by insecurity.

Gender parity in tertiary education showed significance only in the short run, with a one unit increase in GPISET leading to an increase of 6.837 units in output growth. This short-term positive impact highlights the role of advanced skills and innovation, typically developed at higher education levels, in enhancing productivity. In the long run, the impact of GPISET is positive but insignificant, resulting in an increase of 0.420 units in output growth. The loss of significance for tertiary parity over time may be linked to underemployment of graduates and inefficiencies in Nigeria's labor market, as noted by Lawanson and Umar (2019). This situation suggests that Nigeria's labor market is not fully absorbing or utilizing the skills of female graduates. As a result, policies should focus on reforms that align higher education more closely with labor market needs through targeted vocational training, entrepreneurship support, and efforts to tackle workplace gender discrimination.

Additionally, government spending on education has a positive but insignificant effect on output growth in both the short run and the long run. A one unit increase in GEX results in increases of 0.440 and 0.302 units in output growth, respectively. This indicates a possible inefficiency in resource allocation and utilization. While increasing education's share of the national budget is important, it must also involve strategically targeting funds towards gender-sensitive programs with measurable outcomes, especially those that ensure equitable access

and quality learning. The error correction term of -0.537 indicates a high rate of adjustment, with about 53.7% of short-term errors corrected in the long run.

Post-estimation diagnostics tests in Table 6 confirmed the robustness of the model. The high R^2 value (0.85) shows that the explanatory variables account for 85% of the variation in output growth, indicating a strong model fit. The Durbin-Watson statistic (1.98) and Breusch-Godfrey test results show no autocorrelation, while the Breusch-Pagan-Godfrey test confirms that residuals are homoscedastic. The Ramsey RESET test indicates a correct functional form, and the Jarque-Bera statistic confirms the normality of residuals. From figure 1, the stability tests using CUSUM and CUSUM of Squares confirm that the model's coefficients remained stable throughout the study period, emphasizing the reliability of the estimated parameters for inference.

5. Conclusion and Policy Recommendations

This study examined the impact of gender inequality in education on Nigeria's output growth, using endogenous growth theory as a foundation. Education builds skills and knowledge, and equal access for both men and women is essential to enhancing the country's productive capacity. The empirical results reveal that closing gender gaps in education goes beyond fairness; it also plays a crucial role in driving economic growth. Notably, gender parity in primary and secondary school enrollment shows significant positive effects on output growth, underscoring the importance of ensuring equal educational opportunities at these stages.

While gender parity in tertiary education and literacy rates showed some positive effects, these were either limited to the short run or statistically insignificant over the long run. This suggests that improvements at higher education levels alone may not translate into sustained growth without complementary reforms in the labor market. In particular, underemployment and skills mismatches constrain the ability of tertiary graduates to contribute fully to economic productivity.

Given these findings, achieving gender equality in primary and secondary education should be central to Nigeria's development strategy. Policies should focus on reducing barriers for girls through measures such as scholarships, free school meals, and targeted outreach in rural and underserved areas. These interventions directly address factors limiting female enrollment and retention, thereby harnessing the significant growth benefits linked to parity at these levels. Furthermore, supporting girls' transition from primary to secondary education is essential, as the long-run positive impact of secondary parity on output growth highlights the value of sustained educational attainment. Mentorship programs and community engagement initiatives may help improve retention and completion rates among female students.

To maximize the benefits of tertiary education parity, the government should address labor market challenges that limit the long-term impact of higher education on growth. Improving job matching, promoting entrepreneurship, and aligning curricula with labor market demands will help ensure that investments in tertiary education translate into real economic gains, particularly for women.

Although government spending on education showed no statistically significant direct effect on output growth, it remains critical that resources are used efficiently and strategically. Investments should prioritize improving teacher quality, supporting gender-inclusive programs, and focusing on interventions with measurable outcomes in enrollment and retention. Additionally, linking secondary education with vocational training, apprenticeships, and skills development will help align educational outcomes with current labor market needs, addressing structural barriers that limit the immediate economic impact of secondary-level parity.

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